

Supply Chain Management: A Client Focusing Advance

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Abstract

This theme batch with the exploratory conception of supply chain management (SCM). It emphasizes on customer serve in supply chain management for construction effective supply chain network. The customer service elements are a Major voice for improving the execution of an enterprise. In order to achieve this, a total system perspective is necessary for depth psychology of activities. It also focuses the need and wants of customer to residue the business portfolio. This paper describes a formal system analysis utilizing merchandising philosophical system.

Introduction

In the present scenario of globalization and customer service supply chain management is becoming significant to the corporate world. Companies are dealing with consumers through suppliers, distributors, and retailers. They want to deal with their customer directly. On the other hand consumer's demands are increasing. So companies must acquire suitable strategies for immediate flow of product and information throughout their supply chain network. The main theme is to manage customer service in order to attract, enhance and retain customers. It acts as an antidote for building long term relationships with potential customers. Customer relations help to operate the front office functions of sales, marketing and customer services. Customer relations are a marketing function and target the profitable customer (Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995). Marien (2000) lays out the four key enablers' viz. organizational infrastructure, technology, strategic alliances and human resource management that are the key aspect of supply chain management effectiveness. Customer Relationship is technology driven. The main components include ways of customer contact like telephone, mail, personal selling, after sales service etc, call centers, automatic complaint handling, electronic point of sales and integrated information system for digital world. The major thing is to gather and segment information in order to develop customer insight for effective business. The objective of supply chain management and customer relations is not different. The purpose of implementing supply chain management

is to ascertain higher customer satisfaction, increasing profit, expanding revenue base, reducing inventory, lowering product cost and increasing reliability of products (Sahay et.al.2000) This trend confirms the finding at global level by many scholars (Cooper et al. 1993, Lambert & Pagh, 1998; Bowersox & closs, 1989;)

Pyramid of customer service: Financial and market share impact Service elements

- Information sharing
- Delivery innovations
- Direct store delivery Creativity Gain
- Packaging innovation
- Willingness to environment
- Emergency coverage
- Product recall Resilience Maintain
- Response to customer enquiry
- Ease of order entry
- On time delivery Reliability Lose
- Order cycle time
- Condition of order on arrival
- Clerical accuracy

The customer service pyramid divides service capabilities into three types, as shown in Fig(1). These are Reliability, Resilience, and creativity.

Reliability: It means performing the basic well, i.e. Short order cycle times, delivering on time, processing paper work accurately and making proper shipment. Now –a-days reliability does not make a company, which is inefficient in customer service.

Resilience: It is the ability to respond to failures of the customer service systems. To achieve this a company must offer an effective rush – order shipment capability, provide proactive communication of changes in order status, maintain effective shipment – tracking capabilities and immediately respond comprehensively to customer’s enquiries.

Creativity: It mean developing value added programme for customers like shipment to store location, innovation that reduces handling cost. It involves a willingness to experiment and an operating flexibility to create programme that add value.

Companies must develop programmes in all three tiers. They must have the base or reliability. But to increase market share, they have to develop capabilities and programmes at the resilience and creativity levels.

Essence of Customer Service Survey

A focused supply chain management and customer service strategy that is supported by all parts of organization is still only a dream in many companies. So a complete customer service is needed which accomplishes the following:-

Provide a quantitative understanding of the customer requirements.

Measure the relative importance of each element of customer service.

Assess the performance of company and its major competitors.

Provide an understanding of relative significance of customer service issues in customers over all buying decision.

The survey can provide a clear direction to the supply chain management (SCM) function, allowing it to focus its full energies on creating and managing a system, which achieve the consensus customer service goal.

Customer Segmentation for SCM Advantage

Supply Chain Managers can provide considerable value to their by understanding these requirements is account segmentation. A delivery requirements. A very powerful tool for understanding these requirements is account segmentation. A company can use account segmentation to identify market segments, which is well positioned to serve and then organize its products and service in a superior way. The company must tailor its supply chain offerings to meet the needs of each of the market segment it serves. For example, one consumer goods manufacturer segmented its customers based on their operating sophistication and merchandising philosophies. Customers' operating sophistications is determined by the degree of development of their information system and operating method. Their merchandising philosophies included such as sales approaches as "every day low prices" (EDLP) and "deal oriented".

The customer service requirements and demand for supply chain and marketing services differ for each of the segment. For example a pipeline manager has different stock availability, lead time requirement than the traditional retailers. Bulk seller requires different shipment configurations and delivery requirements from other segments.

Supply chain manager will be most successful if they recognize these important operational differences.

Managing Supply Chain to Customer Needs

Customer Oriented Companies need to build leading edge supply chain management system. For this five areas must be addressed.

1. Understanding customer service need
 - Which customer servicing elements are important to the customer?
 - What performance levels are acceptable?
 - What value added capability can give the company a distinctive edge?
2. Structure and operating policies
 - How many distribution centers should a company have? where should the location be?
 - What are the costs and customer service implications of supply chain network design?
 - What types of supply chain network configuration make the best strategic sense?
3. Organization

Integrated supply chain management requires careful design of the three elements. They are organization structure, customer need and culture of each company.

Role and Responsibilities

In a stable environment each function manages independently. In an uncertain or dynamic environment a close working relationship among function is needed and operated in an integrated way. Performance measure: Performance is measured according to desired result. It is determined taking into consideration several inputs and its outputs.

Information System: Three aspects of this system are important.

Timely and accurate information.

Integrated applications software which allow a "What if" simulation of the cost and customer service.

Channel Integration: The efficiency will increase by integrating the supply chain management system with the suppliers and customers.

Creating the Perfect Order

The perfect order is designed to measure the effectiveness of a particular function. It measures the percentage of orders that proceed through every step of order management process without any

fault. Each step must go smoothly for the order to consider as a perfect one. 1. Order entry 2. Credit clearance 3. Inventory availability 4. Accurate picking 5. On time delivery 6. Correct invoicing

Order Management Process

“Re-engineering” the order management functions can shorten order cycle times, improves the consistency in order cycle times, reduce administrative cost and enhance customer satisfaction.

Main things, which are considered, are as follows:

Think beyond order entry or order processing:

Set targets of quantum improvements not incremental change.

Relentlessly seek speed. Eliminate dead time, not value-added activities and waiting time where an order sits. Design the process so that order flow.

Leverage technology where needed:

Utilize measures like the “perfect order” which assess the percentage of orders that are error free and do not require manual interventions.

Companies have integrated order management and supply chain into an align supply chain strategies to meet expanding customer requirements, lowering cost at the same time.

Conclusion

Supply chain manager can play an important role in assuring that their function are customer driven. Companies are differentiating themselves from their competitors on the basis of supply chain excellence. A thorough understanding of customers’ supply chain requirements is required to achieve distinction. It is essential that they manage their activities in a logical way in order to align with these customer needs.

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